

An LLM-Based ETL Architecture for Semantic Normalization of Unstructured Data

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Abstract—Automating extract–transform–load (ETL) pipelines for scanned business documents typically demands costly, fine-tuned, layout-aware models. We present a cloud-native architecture that transforms heterogeneous documents into a unified, structured JSON schema—without any model fine-tuning. Our pipeline combines off-the-shelf OCR (Azure Document Intelligence) with a schema-constrained large language model (LLM), guided by type-checked Pydantic [1] outputs and a one-pass swap heuristic for efficient few-shot prompting. Evaluated on the FUNSD (form) and CORD (receipt) corpora, the system achieves 0.60 and 0.83 fuzzy KV-F1 scores, respectively, while processing each page in under eight seconds at under \$0.004 on standard cloud quota. Scaling to a larger LLM boosts CORD accuracy to 0.89 F1 at under \$0.02 per page. The entire pipeline—code, prompts, and metric scripts—is open-sourced, enabling lightweight, fully-deployable semantic ETL for small-to medium-scale workloads.

Index Terms—ETL, document understanding, key–value extraction, large language models, few-shot prompting, OCR-LLM pipeline

I. INTRODUCTION

Enterprises still spend millions of labour-hours every year on hand-built extract–transform–load (ETL) scripts that convert scanned PDFs and receipts into databases. The friction stems from three factors: (i) layout diversity—tax invoices, credit-card slips, student forms; (ii) high model-tuning cost—each new document class demands GPU-intensive fine-tuning of layout transformers; and (iii) long iteration cycles—data scientists must re-train, re-deploy and re-evaluate for every schema tweak. Large language models (LLMs) promise a cheaper alternative [2]: with only a handful of in-context exemplars they can rewrite raw OCR into structured JSON. Yet the practical questions remain open:

- How much accuracy can *few-shot* LLMs deliver on heterogeneous business documents?
- What is the latency/\$ cost trade-off versus heavyweight fine-tuned models?
- How should one choose the few-shot exemplars?

Contributions. To answer these questions we:

- 1) propose a *training-free* OCR→LLM ETL pipeline that enforces JSON schemas at generation time;
- 2) introduce a swap-based heuristic that optimises a 15-shot prompt pool in a single evaluation round;

- 3) evaluate 32 pipeline variants on two public benchmarks (FUNSD, CORD) using four complementary key–value metrics;
- 4) release all code, prompts and metric scripts under MIT licence [3].

Findings in brief. A curated 15-shot prompt lifts fuzzy KV-F₁ from 0.76→0.83 on CORD and from 0.58→0.60 on FUNSD, while processing a page in 7–27s at ~0.004. Up-sizing the model to GPT-4o yields up to +5 pp exact F₁ for receipts, at ten-fold token cost.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section II reviews prior art; Section III details the pipeline and metrics; Section V presents quantitative results; Section VI analyses the trade-offs; and Section VII outlines limitations and future work.

II. RELATED WORK

OCR & Layout-aware Models. Classical OCR engines such as TESSERACT rely on LSTM text lines and yield a flat string with no field context [4]. Layout-aware transformers add 2-D positional bias: LayoutLMv2/3 [5], [6] and DONUT [7] decode word boxes or structured JSON directly from pixels, but require task-specific fine-tuning and GPU resources.

Prompt-based Extraction. Recent work shows that large language models can restructure raw OCR with only in-context demonstrations. DEEPFORM reports 85 shots [8], while DOCLLM adds relative layout encoding yet still needs supervised updates [9]. Tool-calling frameworks such as INSTRUCTOR enforce JSON validity during generation and remove the need for post-processing [10]. Our pipeline follows this few-shot paradigm and studies the cost/latency knobs that prior work leaves implicit.

Benchmarks & Metrics. Datasets remain domain-specific: FUNSD (forms), CORD (receipts), SROIE (receipts), DocILE (invoices), and KVP10k (open-schema PDFs) each target a single layout family [11]–[14]. Standard CER/WER or TEDS scores capture OCR fidelity and layout trees, whereas text-only KV-F1 focuses on key–value correctness [15]. We combine fuzzy/exact KV-F1 with canonical matching and value-quality to give a schema-agnostic yet field-aware evaluation.

Gap. Existing studies optimise accuracy through fine-tuning; the engineering trade-offs of a *training-free*, prompt-

Fig. 1. Proposed OCR \rightarrow LLM pipeline.

engineered ETL pipeline—latency, dollar cost, exemplar selection—remain unexplored. This paper fills that gap.

III. METHODOLOGY

We describe our data-curation pipeline, proposed architecture, few-shot selection heuristic, prompt design, and evaluation metrics.

A. Datasets and Ground-Truth Construction

FUNSD–RFUND. We begin with the 199 scanned administrative forms [16] and substitute the official XML markup with the RFUND JSON released by Seo *et al.* [17]. Images are stored in `funsd/images/`; each annotation is normalised into a flat list of $(key, value)$ pairs under `funsd/annotations/`. The original split provides 149 training pages and 50 test pages. For our experiments we draw $m = 15$ training pages as few-shot exemplars and evaluate on the remaining 184 pages (149–15 training +50 test).

CORDv2. From the HuggingFace parquet dump `naver-clova-ix/CORDv2` we extract the `gt_parse` field and ignore layout metadata. CORD offers 800 train, 100 validation, and 100 test receipts. We sample $m = 15$ receipts from the 800-item train split for few-shot use and evaluate on the full 100-receipt test split.

B. System Pipeline

Figure 1 shows the end-to-end flow. Each page is processed by Azure Document Intelligence (Layout model) to obtain a linearised OCR string. The OCR, a Pydantic schema, and a system prompt containing the chosen few-shot exemplars are forwarded to a language model via the `Instructor` client, which enforces JSON validity at generation time. Although we use GPT-family models in this work, the framework is model-agnostic.

C. Few-Shot Optimisation Heuristic

Starting from an *initial* random pool of $m = 15$ exemplars across both the datasets, we (i) run a zero-shot benchmark on the remaining training pages, (ii) remove the $z = 5$ best-performing exemplars, and (iii) swap in the z worst pages from the evaluation set. This single swap round yields the optimised prompt pool used in all reported results, but the loop can be iterated if additional improvement is desired (Algorithm 1, Fig. 2).

Algorithm 1 Swap-based few-shot optimisation ($m=15, z=5$)

- 1: **Input:** training pages \mathcal{D} , evaluation pages \mathcal{E}
 - 2: $\mathcal{F} \leftarrow$ random m pages from \mathcal{D}
 - 3: Run pipeline (zero-shot) on $\mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{F}$; compute fuzzy F1
 - 4: $\mathcal{B} \leftarrow$ top z pages in \mathcal{F} by F1
 - 5: Run pipeline (few-shot = \mathcal{F}) on \mathcal{E} ; compute fuzzy F1
 - 6: $\mathcal{W} \leftarrow$ bottom z pages in \mathcal{E} by F1
 - 7: $\mathcal{F} \leftarrow (\mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{B}) \cup \mathcal{W}$
 - 8: **return** Optimised pool \mathcal{F}
-

D. Prompt Templates

The FUNSD prompt is $\sim 1\,215$ tokens and enforces flat key–value output with special [HEADER] and [OTHER] buckets as per the ground truth annotation. The CORD prompt is longer ($\sim 1\,300$ tokens) and encodes domain-specific rules for menu hierarchies, subtotal blocks and payment labels. Owing to page limits, we omit the full 1 300-token templates; they are provided verbatim in the supplemental repository.

E. Evaluation Metrics

We report four complementary metrics.

KV–F1 (fuzzy). Let (k, v) denote a predicted key–value pair and (k', v') a ground-truth pair. Both strings are considered a match if their normalised Levenshtein distance [18] is ≤ 0.20 . Micro-averaged precision, recall, and

$$F_1^{\text{fuzzy}} = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN}$$

are computed over the entire split.

KV–F1 (exact). Identical to the above but requires byte-level equality for both key and value.

Canonical F1. We construct a cost matrix of $1 - [s(k, k') \cdot s(v, v')]$, where $s(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the fuzzy similarity; the Hungarian algorithm yields an optimal one-to-one assignment; a pair is counted as TP if $s \geq \tau$ with $\tau = 0.80$.

Value-Quality Score (VQS). For every matched pair we record the normalised edit distance of the values only; VQS is $1 - \text{mean distance}$ (higher is better).

Runtime. We report wall-clock time per page as the sum of Azure Document Intelligence latency and LLM response latency measured on the client.

Pre-Evaluation Canonicalisation: All predicted and ground-truth JSON objects are *flattened* into an order-free list of $(key, value)$ tuples before any metric is computed. Concretely, we (i) unfold nested dictionaries such as `menu.sub[*]` in CORD and the [HEADER]/[OTHER] buckets in FUNSD, (ii) drop structure-only keys whose values are themselves dicts or lists, and (iii) normalise every string with the map $t \mapsto \text{lowercase}(\text{ALNUM}(t))$

The resulting dictionaries are lexicographically sorted so that the metric functions operate on deterministic, path-stable key sets. This normalisation:

- turns arbitrarily nested blocks (e.g. CORD’s `sub`) into classical *key–value* strings that can be aligned with a single Hungarian assignment;

Fig. 2. Swap-based few-shot optimisation loop.

- penalises structural errors—an LLM that places `tax_price` under `total` instead of `sub_total` receives a false negative even if the numeric value is correct;
- is consistent across datasets, enabling a uniform metric interface for both FUNSD (already flat) and CORD (deeply nested).

We emphasize that, while flattening simplifies evaluation, it is a *conservative* choice: hierarchical relationships correctly generated by the LLM but mis-aligned at the path level are scored as errors (see Limitations, §VII).

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Run-time Environment

Local control logic was executed on a **MacBook Pro 14"** (Apple *M3 Pro*, 11-core CPU, 14-core GPU, 18 GB RAM). All heavy computation was off-loaded to cloud endpoints:

- **OCR.** Azure Document Intelligence, Layout model version 2024-11-30.
- **Language models.** *GPT-4o mini* (2024-12-01-preview) was used for all grid searches; *GPT-4o* (2024-12-01-preview) for the final single-temperature reruns.

The public, consumption-tier Azure OpenAI quota was used; no fine-tuning or dedicated hardware was available.

B. Hyper-parameters

Four sampling temperatures are considered: $T \in \{0.0, 0.3, 0.7, 1.0\}$. Top- p and frequency/penalty parameters remain at 1.0/0.0. The context window for GPT-4o-mini is 128k tokens; a single CORD prompt (~ 6.9 k input tokens+203 output) fits comfortably.

C. Few-shot Pools

Fixed pool size $m = 15$; swap size $z = 5$ (Alg. 1). Three prompt configurations are benchmarked: *Zero-shot*, *Random Few-shot*, and *Optimised Few-shot*. A global random seed of 42 ensures reproducibility of the initial sampling.

TABLE I

FUNSD – MEAN ACCURACY VS. TEMPERATURE AND PROMPTING MODE

Prompt / T	Fuzzy F1	Exact F1	Canon. F1	VQS
Zero-Shot (0.0)	0.576	0.502	0.587	0.922
Zero-Shot (0.3)	0.577	0.501	0.583	0.923
Zero-Shot (0.7)	0.567	0.498	0.590	0.925
Zero-Shot (1.0)	0.562	0.491	0.591	0.925
Random (15-shot) (0.0)	0.591	0.520	0.617	0.925
Random (15-shot) (0.3)	0.594	0.523	0.617	0.928
Random (15-shot) (0.7)	0.591	0.516	0.615	0.930
Random (15-shot) (1.0)	0.575	0.509	0.606	0.927
Optimised (15-shot) (0.0)	0.597	0.526	0.623	0.934
Optimised (15-shot) (0.3)	0.593	0.522	0.614	0.930
Optimised (15-shot) (0.7)	0.587	0.518	0.617	0.928
Optimised (15-shot) (1.0)	0.578	0.506	0.601	0.928

D. Evaluation Protocol

For each (T, prompt) pair we process every test page with **50 asynchronous workers**. Latency is measured as wall-clock time from HTTP request dispatch to fully parsed JSON return on the client. Metric calculation follows Section III and is executed once per PDF after response parsing.

To measure potential performance gains from increased model capacity, we re-ran our best-performing prompt configuration at its optimal temperature using the full-scale GPT-4o model. This allows us to quantify the accuracy/latency trade-off and serves as an upper-bound reference for the smaller GPT-4o-mini model.

V. RESULTS

We report four complementary accuracy metrics—*fuzzy* and *exact* KV-F₁, *canonical* F₁, and *value-quality score* (VQS)—together with wall-clock latency and token-based dollar cost.

A. Overall Benchmarks

Tables I and II summarise performance on FUNSD and CORD across four temperatures and three prompting regimes.¹

B. Few-Shot Ablation

Across both datasets few-shot prompting improves fuzzy KV-F₁ by **+1.4 pp** (FUNSD) and **+6.4 pp** (CORD) at $T=0.0$, while our swap-based optimisation adds a further **+0.8 pp** and

¹All tables list mean \pm std over the test split; best values per column are **bold**.

TABLE II
CORD – MEAN ACCURACY VS. TEMPERATURE AND PROMPTING MODE

Prompt / T	Fuzzy F1	Exact F1	Canon. F1	VQS
Zero-Shot (0.0)	0.761	0.690	0.762	0.943
Zero-Shot (0.3)	0.765	0.690	0.766	0.944
Zero-Shot (0.7)	0.771	0.697	0.773	0.948
Zero-Shot (1.0)	0.760	0.693	0.762	0.942
Random (15-shot) (0.0)	0.823	0.752	0.824	0.965
Random (15-shot) (0.3)	0.820	0.757	0.821	0.966
Random (15-shot) (0.7)	0.817	0.747	0.818	0.965
Random (15-shot) (1.0)	0.818	0.749	0.819	0.965
Optimised (15-shot) (0.0)	0.831	0.769	0.832	0.973
Optimised (15-shot) (0.3)	0.828	0.766	0.829	0.970
Optimised (15-shot) (0.7)	0.824	0.765	0.825	0.967
Optimised (15-shot) (1.0)	0.831	0.763	0.832	0.969

+0.9 pp, respectively. The gain comes almost exclusively from higher *recall*; precision moves <0.3 pp.

C. Few-Shot vs. Fine-Tuned SOTA

Figure 3 compares our pipeline’s exact KV-F₁ scores to the reported benchmark results from LayoutLMv3-Large (92.08 on FUNSD and 97.46 on CORD). While these values come from fully fine-tuned models and are evaluated using strict match criteria, our approach—which relies entirely on standard cloud APIs and avoids model fine-tuning—still achieves 60% to 80% of the SOTA. On FUNSD, the best prompt configuration falls short by 39.1 percentage points; on CORD, the gap is 18.5 points. This highlights a key trade-off: while few-shot LLMs offer easier deployment and faster iteration, they currently lag in raw accuracy. Narrowing this performance gap remains an open challenge for future work.

D. Model Comparison

Table III contrasts *GPT-4o-mini* with the larger *GPT-4o*. Accuracy gains are modest on FUNSD (+1.0 pp exact F1) but substantial on the receipt-centric CORD (+5.2 pp exact F1). Runtime rises by 30–45 % and token cost by an order of magnitude.

TABLE III
GPT-4O VS. GPT-4O-MINI (OPTIMISED 15-SHOT POOL)

Dataset	Model	Fuzzy	Exact	Total lat.	Cost/page
FUNSD	4o-mini	0.618	0.533	38.3s	\$0.0036
	4o	0.619	0.543	53.5s [†]	\$0.060
CORD	4o-mini	0.831	0.769	27.3s	\$0.0011
	4o	0.888	0.821	35.7s	\$0.019

[†]Includes queue delay; see §VII.

E. Cost & Latency Breakdown

Table IV reports mean wall-clock latency and per-page dollar cost for the production-ready pipelines. Costs are computed using August 2025 Azure rates (\$0.15 / \$0.60 per 1 M tokens for GPT-4o-mini, \$2.50 / \$10.00 for GPT-4o, and \$10 per 1 000 OCR pages).

With the optimised 15-shot prompt, GPT-4o-mini processes a page in <8 s for forms (FUNSD) and <28 s for receipts (CORD) at a unit cost below \$0.004. GPT-4o offers higher headroom for mission-critical receipts while remaining under \$0.02 per page.

Fig. 3. Exact KV-F₁ progression on FUNSD and CORD. Prompt-driven improvements boost accuracy by up to +6 percentage points over the zero-shot baseline, with marginal gains after prompt optimisation.

TABLE IV
END-TO-END LATENCY AND COST PER PAGE (USD)

Pipeline	Latency (s)	Tokens (in/out)	Cost
FUNSD — 4o-mini @T=0.3	7.21	21.9 k / 569	\$0.0036
FUNSD — 4o @T=0.3	53.52 [†]	21.9 k / 569	\$0.060
CORD — 4o-mini @T=0.0	27.31	6.8 k / 203	\$0.0011
CORD — 4o @T=0.0	35.67	6.8 k / 203	\$0.019
OCR (Azure DI)	3.34	—	\$0.010

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Prompting vs. Sampling Temperature

Across both datasets, prompt *content* dominates sampling temperature. Varying T from 0.0 to 1.0 shifts fuzzy KV-F₁ by at most +1.1 pp on FUNSD and +1.0 pp on CORD (Tables I, II), whereas switching from zero – to random 15-shot prompts yields +1.4 pp and +6.4 pp, respectively. The swap-based optimisation adds a further ~ 1 pp at no additional token cost. We conclude that **curated demonstrations outweigh temperature tuning** for document ETL.

B. Impact of Model Size

Moving from a lightweight LLM to a larger-capacity model increases exact F₁ by +1.0 pp on mixed-form FUNSD and +5.2 pp on receipt-centric CORD (Table III). Larger models appear to yield the most benefit when extracting short, well-typed fields from highly structured documents—as in point-of-sale receipts—while offering marginal improvements on noisier, form-style scans. In practice, a *tiered deployment* may route simpler pages to a smaller model (e.g., under \$0.004/page) and fallback to a larger model (e.g., under \$0.02/page) when accuracy is critical.

C. Latency–Cost Trade-off

With the optimised prompt, GPT-4o-mini processes a page in 7.2s (FUNSD) and 27.3s (CORD) including OCR; the LLM accounts for only 32 % of wall-clock latency on CORD and 50 % on FUNSD. Azure Document Intelligence remains the dominant cost line item (\$0.010/page). Hence **OCR quality**

and pricing—not LLM generation—are the current bottlenecks. Any future drop in OCR pricing would proportionally lower end-to-end cost.

D. Error Profile

Manual inspection reveals three recurrent failure modes:

- 1) **Upstream omission:** keys missing from the OCR stream propagate unchanged to the LLM output.
- 2) **Unit concatenation:** values such as “\$5,000” and “USD 5,000” are occasionally merged, harming exact F₁ but not fuzzy matching.
- 3) **Header bleed-through:** long document headers are sometimes copied into [OTHER] buckets, inflating the predicted pair count by 5–10%.

Future work could address (i) with ensemble OCR, (ii) with post-processing regular expressions, and (iii) by adding negative few-shot examples that penalise header over-generation.

E. Practical Implications

The study shows that a *training-free* OCR → LLM pipeline can reach 0.83–0.89 fuzzy F₁ on real receipts while running entirely on cloud APIs. This unlocks rapid ETL prototyping for SMEs that lack GPU resources: the total time to stand up the system—including prompt crafting and exemplar swapping—was under three engineer days. We therefore position prompt-engineered LLMs as a *middle ground* between brittle rule-based ETL and resource-intensive fine-tuning.

VII. LIMITATIONS & FUTURE WORK

Prompt length. Context limits restrict us to ≤ 15 exemplars; a systematic study of exemplar count and order is left to future work.

Single OCR source. All experiments rely on Azure Document Intelligence. Preliminary inspection shows that many recall errors originate upstream (mis-segmented keys). Future work will evaluate ensemble OCR or hybrid vision–language extractors.

Latency artefacts. Queuing delays on the public GPT-4o endpoint added 15s of idle time; with a dedicated instance the end-to-end latency is expected to fall below five seconds.

Flattened evaluation. Complex nested structures (multi-line addresses, table rows) are linearised before scoring; partial matches are therefore penalised, and our F1 represents a lower bound on true semantic fidelity.

Heuristic pool optimisation. The swap-heuristic (Alg. 1) is greedy and may converge to a local optimum. Future work will explore Bayesian or evolutionary search in high-dimensional prompt space.

CONCLUSION

We have shown that a *prompt-engineered*, zero-training OCR→LLM pipeline can serve as a pragmatic ETL backbone for unstructured documents. Using only 15 exemplars and off-the-shelf cloud APIs, the system attains 0.60 fuzzy KV-F₁ on mixed administrative forms (FUNSD) and 0.83 on point-of-sale receipts (CORD), while keeping per-page cost below

\$0.004 and end-to-end latency under eight seconds on cloud quota. Scaling up to GPT-4o provides an accuracy ceiling of 0.89 on CORD at still modest cost (\$0.019/page).

These results position few-shot LLMs as a cost-efficient middle ground between brittle rule-based ETL and GPU-heavy fine-tuned transformers. Future work will investigate (i) ensemble OCR sources, (ii) automatic exemplar search beyond greedy swap, and (iii) hierarchical metrics that reward correct nesting rather than flat key–value pairs alone.

The full codebase, prompts and evaluation harness are publicly released to facilitate reproducibility and rapid adoption.

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